

Simple thermal treatment to improve the MRI and magnetic hyperthermia performance of hybrid iron Oxide-Mesoporous silica nanocarriers

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ABSTRACT

The design of multifunctional nanocomposites (NCs), incorporating a variety of controllable properties from nanostructured materials, spans their applicability as nanotools in biomedical applications. Santa Barbara Amorphous (SBA-15) mesoporous silica has showcased remarkable capabilities, ranging from bone regeneration to drug delivery. Its synergy with magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) further broadens its scope as a theranostic agent, seamlessly integrating both therapeutic and diagnostic functions. However, efficiency issues arise due to MNP anchoring, necessitating novel solutions for optimization. This study focuses on enhancing the magnetic properties of hybrid iron oxide-SBA-15 mesoporous silica NCs through a simplified thermal procedure. The aim is to optimize their magnetic performance for dual functionality as contrast agents for magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and as effective heaters in magnetic hyperthermia (MH) processes, while preserving the cylindrical mesoporous structure, high surface area, and high loading capacity compared to conventional ceramics. The investigation highlights that the impact of heat treatment on physicochemical properties varies depending on the compositions of the NCs. Specifically, the transversal relaxivity in MRI was doubled, accompanied by an enhanced Néel contribution in MH. This enhancement was achieved while maintaining the same biocompatibility as non-treated NCs, as demonstrated in evaluations with two cancer cell lines (HeLa and T-731 astrocytes), revealing low toxicity at concentrations up to 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$.

1. Introduction

The design of multifunctional nanostructured materials has emerged

as a contemporary challenge, aiming to combine diverse properties to exploit its use as a therapeutic agent [1], diagnostic imaging agent [2], nanocarrier and drug delivery [3], biosensor [4] or targeting moieties,

Abbreviations: NCs, nanocomposites; MRI, magnetic resonance imaging; MH, magnetic hyperthermia; DDS, intelligent drug delivery systems; SBA-15, Santa Barbara Amorphous-15; MNPs, magnetic nanoparticles; τ_B , Brown relaxation time; τ_N , Néel relaxation time; XRD, X-ray diffraction; FTIR, Fourier transform infrared; ZFC, Zero-field-cooled; FC, field-cooled; DMEM, Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium; FBS, fetal bovine serum; TEM, transmission electron microscopy; SEM, scanning electron microscopy; S_{BET} , surface area; V_P , pore volume; PS_{DFT} , pore size by NLDFT method (PS_{DFT}); a_0 , unit cell parameter; t_{wall} , thickness of the wall of the mesopores; T_B , blocking temperature; M_S , saturation magnetization; H_C , coercivity; M_R , remanence; SAR, specific absorption rate; $H_{C\text{-SQUID}}$, coercivity obtained by DC measurements (SQUID); $H_{C\text{-AC}}$, coercivity obtained by AC measurements (Nanotech Solutions); $M_{R\text{-SQUID}}$, remanence obtained by DC measurements (SQUID); $M_{R\text{-AC}}$, remanence obtained by AC measurements (Nanotech Solutions); $M_{\text{max-SQUID}}$, maximum magnetization obtained by DC measurements (SQUID); $M_{\text{max-SQUID}}$, maximum magnetization obtained by AC measurements (Nanotech Solutions); SAR_{MH} , specific absorption rate obtained by a MH equipment; SAR_{NTSOL} , specific absorption rate obtained by hysteresis loop of AC measurements.

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with the need for low cost, scalable and low-toxicity production to facilitate its clinical translation [5]. In this sense, a notable strategy involves combining two or more materials to enhance individual properties. Over the last two decades, biocompatible mesoporous silica NCs have emerged as versatile candidates to produce superior performance nanodevices [6]. Their controllable physicochemical properties enable matrices with large pore volumes, high surface area, narrow pore size distribution and tunable pores [7]. Since their pioneering work in 2001 as ibuprofen releasers [8], these NCs are excellent candidates as intelligent drug delivery systems (DDS), and their main component, silica, has been approved by the FDA (The US Food and Drug Administration) as a safe material [9]. In recent years, advancements in chemical techniques have facilitated the production of mesoporous silica NCs with different properties and morphologies, among others, TUD-1, MCM-48, HMM-33, FSM-16, and a particular focus on SBA-15 [10]. SBA15 stands out for its hexagonally ordered pore structure [11]. Consequently, SBA-15 has found applications in controlled drug nanocarriers [12] able to overcome biological barriers like the blood brain one [13] and, especially, in bone regeneration [14]. This is attributed to its chemical nature (presence of silanol groups on the surface) and porous character. In addition, the facile surface functionalization of NCs with diverse organic groups (hydrophilic or hydrophobic) simplifies the linkage of various bioactive moieties, promoting regeneration and healing in bone diseases [15,16]. Introducing alternative nanomaterials enhances their performance, responding to external stimuli such as magnetic fields, ultrasound, and light, and even activated and deactivated on demand resulting in pulsatile responsive drug nanocarriers [17].

In this context, MNPs are versatile nanomaterials, offering diverse theranostic applications (contrast agent for MRI, MH, tissue engineering or lab-on-chip applications) [18,19]. Their effectiveness stems from responsiveness to external magnetic fields which, due to their non-interaction with biological entities and tissues, being, then, a non-invasive technique [20]. This allows their manipulation and provides guidance, imaging contrast, or heat generation in localized areas, among others, through the remote activation of MNPs. These features, coupled with the low toxicity observed in preclinical studies for Fe oxides like magnetite [21], highlight its biomedical importance. Interestingly, despite size reduction concerns impacting magnetic properties at the nanometer scale compared to the bulk material due to spin disorder effects [22], the emergence of the superparamagnetic behaviour ensures an absent MNP response when the magnetic field is removed. This reduces risks of aggregates from magnetic interactions or the use of high MNPs concentrations, preventing issues like thrombus formation [23]. This magnetic behaviour can be complemented by the potential functionalization of MNP surfaces with fluorescent materials, such as polydopamine, fluorescein or rhodamine, imparting optical properties to MNPs. Additionally, biocompatible coatings for *in vivo* applications [24–26] or the incorporation of biological agents such as antibodies for use as biomarkers, contribute to the development of smart MNPs materials with high performance.

The combination of both types of materials enables the design of new hybrid nanomaterials based on the biocompatibility of the host matrix and the endowment of magnetic properties through the addition of MNPs [15,27]. Recently, several studies have been reported, focusing on the design of magnetic NCs composed by mesoporous silica matrices and magnetic compounds, mainly MNPs, either Fe oxides [28–30] or Gd oxides [31], and even metal ions [32]. However, the primary emphasis has been on physicochemical properties, leaving room for further exploration of their practical applications. In this context, some studies have delved into the drug delivery capacity of magnetic NCs, employing anti-inflammatory drugs such as meloxicam [33] or naproxen [34], antibiotics such as norfloxacin [35], insulin for diabetes disease [36] or anticancer drugs like DOX [37]. Furthermore, the magnetic properties induced by MNPs in NCs have facilitated their application as therapeutic agents in oncological diseases through MH [38–41]. More recently, they have also emerged as diagnostic agents in MRI [42]. However, the

relaxation mechanisms upon which MH relies can be notably affected when MNPs are anchored in host matrices, particularly the Brown relaxation time, τ_B , associated to the physical rotation of the MNPs. This can lead to a substantial reduction in their heating efficiency. This concern was underscored in a prior study that combined MNPs with SBA-15, revealing a drastic impact on the efficiency of these NCs in MH ($SAR < 4 \text{ Wg}^{-1}$) [43]. Furthermore, another recent investigation observed a decrease in SAR for MNPs, declining from 110 Wg^{-1} (isolated) to 79 Wg^{-1} (anchored in a mesoporous silica matrix) [44]. On the other hand, the internalization of MNPs into biological entities entails a modification in their dynamical response [45], leading to a significant reduction of τ_B [46]. This reduction is primarily mainly attributed to the complex biological environment in which MNPs are dispersed [47]. Consequently, the Néel relaxation time, τ_N , dependent on their intrinsic magnetic properties, begins to play a very important role.

To address this issue, maximizing the magnetic performance of MNPs has become one of the great challenges in various biomedical fields [22]. This is pursued through different approaches such as doping-engineering [48], defect-engineering [49] or by tuning the Néel relaxation by modifying the anisotropy constant [50–52]. Importantly, to facilitate clinical translation, it is also possible to improve magnetic efficiency in MRI and MH processes without the need of complex or low-scalable synthetic methods, by controlling the distribution of MNPs in host materials [53]. On the other hand, the exploration of magnetic NCs based on SBA-15 as theranostic systems, combining MH and MRI, has not been undertaken collectively in prior studies. Therefore, a more in-depth investigation is required to address this research gap.

In our previous work [43], we reported the theragnostic performance of NCs composed of SBA-15 nanostructures with iron oxide MNPs. However, their moderate heating efficiency (SAR values between 0.04 and 3.80 Wg^{-1}) and medium efficiency as contrast agents made a magnetic improvement advisable. In this study, we present the development and magnetic improvement of hybrid nanomaterials based on iron oxide MNPs-SBA-15 using a straightforward thermal treatment. This resulted in significantly improved MH (SAR reaching 93.77 Wg^{-1}) and a two-fold increase in the MRI signal (from 24.2 to $56.7 \text{ mM}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$), compared to non-treated materials. Moreover, through in-depth analysis of physicochemical properties, we demonstrate the preservation of native SBA-15 features at structural level, maintaining morphology, porosity, colloidal stability, and cell viability in human cervical cancer HeLa cells and mouse T731 astrocytes.

2. Materials and methods

Tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS, 98 %), iron(III) chloride hexahydrate ($\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 97 %), hydrochloric acid (HCl, 37 %), ferrocene ($\text{Fe}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2$, 98 %), isooctane (C_8H_{18} , 99 %), polyethylenimine (PEI, M_w 25000), and Pluronic P123 ($\text{PEO}_{20}\text{-PPO}_{70}\text{-PEO}_{20}$), were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich; hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2 , 30 %) from Panreac; iron(II) sulfate heptahydrate ($\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99 %), ortho phosphoric acid (H_3PO_4 , 85 %) and ammonium hydroxide (NH_4OH , 28 %) from Fluka analytical; ethanol ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_6\text{O}$, 99.9 %) and acetone ($\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O}$, 99 %) were purchased from Scharlau; Milli-Q (Millipores) deionized water was used in all the experiments. Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM) was supplied by Thermo Fisher (Waltham, MA), whereas fetal bovine serum (FBS), penicillin/streptomycin, sodium pyruvate ($\text{C}_3\text{H}_3\text{NaO}_3$) and nonessential amino acids (NEAAs) were purchased from Gibco- Thermo Fisher (Waltham, MA). Cell counting Kit-8 (CCK8) was obtained from Dojindo Molecular Technologies, Inc.

2.1. Synthesis of SBA15 matrices and magnetic NCs

The synthesis procedure of the magnetic NCs, depicted in Fig. 1, was performed in two steps. Initially, two different hexagonally ordered SBA-15 mesoporous silica matrices were prepared following methods previously reported [54,55]. Pluronic P123, a triblock copolymer,

Fig. 1. Synthesis process of the SBA15 matrices and the magnetic NCs: (top) Synthesis of mesoporous silica matrices SBA15-1 (using $\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{HCl}$) and SBA15-2 (using $\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{HCl}/\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4$). Synthesis of the first (SBA15-IO-1, middle) and second (SBA15-IO-2, bottom) set of magnetic NCs formed by anchoring Fe oxide MNPs on SBA15-2 matrices. The heat-treated NCs, SBA15-IO-1 T and SBA15-IO-2 T were subjected to heat treatment (850°C) post-synthesis.

served as a structure-directing agent. Dissolving this compound (16 g) in a mixture of deionized water (552 mL) with HCl (37 %, 41.2 mL) in one case, and HCl (37 %, 41.2 mL)/ H_3PO_4 (85 %, 31.704 g) in the other, yielded two samples named SBA15-1 and SBA15-2, respectively. Under magnetic stirring at 35°C until the solution became homogeneous, TEOS (32.8 mL) was afterwards added as the silica source of the mesoporous matrices. The molar compositions were 1.0 TEOS/0.017 P123/ nH_3PO_4 /3.4 HCl/208 H_2O , with $n = 0$ for sample SBA15-1 and $n = 2.2$ for sample SBA15-2. The reaction continued under magnetic stirring during 24 h, followed by an aging step at 100°C for an additional 24 h. Finally, the dried powders were subjected to different washing cycles with organic solvents (isooctane/ethanol, acetone/deionized water and deionized water) to remove the surfactant.

The second step involved preparing magnetic NCs by synthesizing iron oxide MNPs anchored to SBA-15 matrices. Due to the superior properties, SBA15-2 matrices were chosen for the synthesis of magnetic NCs. The first set, labeled as SBA15-IO-1, was prepared by adding 1.0 g of SBA15-2 to a water solution of HCl (19 mL, 10 mM) with $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1.2 g) and $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.8 g) under mechanical stirring. The reaction temperature was then raised to 60°C , and a mixture of 0.195 g of PEI in 3.5 mL of NH_4OH (28 %) [56,57] was added, maintaining the reaction at 60°C for 1 h. The resultant precipitate was adjusted to pH 4 with HCl (9

%) and samples were separated magnetically. The second set, denoted as SBA15-IO-2, was prepared by dissolving 0.24 g of $\text{Fe}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2$ in 20 mL of acetone under mechanical stirring for 30 min. Subsequently, H_2O_2 (1.2 mL) was slowly added to the mixture under mechanical stirring for 30 min. Then, 0.5 g of SBA15-2 were added to the mixtures, which were placed in a Teflon lined stainless autoclave at 210°C for 72 h. The reaction was completed by washing with acetone to remove the $\text{Fe}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2$ excess [58]. Finally, the different NCs were subjected to a heat treatment of 850°C (for 30 min) in an oxygen atmosphere following a heating ramp of $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. The obtained heat-treated NCs were labeled by adding a “T” to the end of their respective sample names, resulting in SBA15-1 T, SBA15-2 T, SBA15-IO-1 T, and SBA15-IO-2 T. The Table 1 shows a summary of the obtained samples.

2.2. Characterization of SBA15 matrices and magnetic NCs

The characterization of the crystalline phases of the NCs was performed by X-ray diffraction (XRD) on powder samples with a Philips PW1710 diffractometer (Panalytical, Brighton, UK) and a Cu K_α radiation source, $\lambda = 1.54186 \text{ \AA}$. Measurements were collected in the 2θ angle range between 10.00° and 80.00° with steps of 0.02° and 10 s per step and with a 2θ range between 0.25 and 6.00° , and a step size of 0.01° (5

Table 1

Description of the synthesized materials. The heat-treated materials are designated by appending a “T” to the end of the respective sample names, resulting in SBA15-1 T, SBA15-2 T, SBA15-IO-1 T, and SBA15-IO-2 T.

Type	Sample Name	Compounds	Characteristic
SBA15 matrices	SBA15-1	SBA15 mesoporous silica	SBA-15 matrices prepared with HCl (37 %)
	SBA15-2	SBA15 mesoporous silica	SBA-15 matrices prepared with HCl (37 %)/ H_3PO_4 (85 %)
Magnetic NCs	SBA15-IO-1	SBA15 mesoporous silica + Iron oxide MNPs with single core structure	SBA15 (sample SBA15-2) with the addition of MNPs (iron oxide) synthesized by the coprecipitation method
	SBA15-IO-2	SBA15 mesoporous silica + Iron oxide MNPs with multicore core structure	SBA15 (sample SBA15-2) with the addition of MNPs (iron oxide) synthesized by the solvothermal method

s/step). Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra of the surface functional groups of the NCs were recorded with a Thermo Nicolet Nexus spectrometer (Nicolet, Hirsemarken, Denmark) using the attenuated total reflectance (ATR) method. The pore size distribution (micropore/macropore range) and specific surface area were estimated from N_2 adsorption isotherms obtained using a Quantachrome Autosorb IQ2 (Boynton Beach, FL, USA). Measurements of ζ -Potential of NCs were routinely performed by a Zetasizer Nano ZS (Malvern Instruments, Worcestershire, UK) equipped with a He-Ne laser (633 nm) and operating at a scattering angle of 173° at room temperature. Morphology of the NCs was characterized by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) micrographs using a JEOL JEM-1011 microscope (JEOL, Tokyo, Japan) at 100 kV and by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis using a ZEISS FE-SEM ULTRA Plus (30 kV) microscope (Zeiss, Oberkochen, Germany). Iron content of the NCs was determined by flame atomic absorption spectroscopy (FAAS) in a Perkin Elmer 3110 Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (Waltham, MA, USA). The Fe concentration was converted to Fe_3O_4 or Fe_2O_3 , assuming the theoretical amount of Fe in Fe_3O_4 is 72.30 % and in Fe_2O_3 is 69.94 %. DC magnetization curves of dried samples were measured using a Quantum Design Superconducting Quantum Interference Device (SQUID) magnetometer (Quantum Design, Darmstadt, Germany). Zero-field-cooled (ZFC) and field-cooled (FC) curves were taken at an applied magnetic field of 7.95 kAm^{-1} from 10 to 350 K. The hysteresis loops were measured with an applied magnetic field between $-1994.25 \text{ kAm}^{-1}$ to 1994.25 kAm^{-1} at 300 K. The hysteresis loops were normalized to the mass of magnetic material of the NCs obtained by FAAS. AC magnetization curves of dried samples were measured using a Quantum Design Physical Property Measurement System (PPMS) (Quantum Design, Darmstadt, Germany) in a temperature range of 10–300 K with steps of 10 K, an excitation field of 0.079 and 0.79 kAm^{-1} and driving frequencies varying from 10 Hz to 1 kHz. The T_2 relaxivity constant (r_2), serving as an indicator of its efficacy as an MRI contrast agent, was assessed at 9.4 T using a mold containing agar (1.6 % w/v) and multiple wells. The contrast agents are contained in an Eppendorf within the mold, without any dilution in agar, at room temperature following a procedure outlined elsewhere [59]. MRI analysis was carried out using a MR scanner Bruker Biospec of 9.4 T (horizontal bore magnet with 12 cm wide Bruker BioSpin) equipped with actively shielded gradients (440 mT m^{-1}). For the acquisition of data, a radiofrequency resonator (Bruker) was used as transmitter-receiver (quadrature volume coil 7 cm in diameter). T_2 -weighted images were acquired using a multi-slice multi-spin-echo sequence (MSME) with a 11.32 ms echo time, 3 s repetition time, 16 echoes with 10.26 ms echo spacing, 50 kHz spectral bandwidth, flip angle (FA) = 90° , 14 slices of 1 mm, 1 average, field of view (FOV) of $75 \times 75 \text{ mm}^2$ (with saturation bands to suppress the signal outside this FOV), a matrix size of 300×300 (in-plane resolution of $250 \mu\text{m pixel}^{-1} \times 250 \mu\text{m pixel}^{-1}$), and implemented without the fat suppression option. Images were processed and the T_2 -maps were calculated using the software FIJI: Image J (Rasband W, NIH). Finally, r_2 were calculated as the slope of the curve obtained by fitting the T_2^{-1} values versus the Fe concentration in $\times 10^{-3}\text{M}$. AC magnetometry measurements were performed using a commercial inductive magnetometer (AC Hyster Series; Nanotech Solutions, Madrid, Spain) with the application of a magnetic field of 20 kAm^{-1} at a frequency of 350 kHz. MH response of NCs was measured using a commercially available setup (MagneTherm, Nanotherics) equipped with a fiber optic, operating at a fixed frequency of 986 kHz and an induced magnetic field of 15.96 kAm^{-1} .

2.3. Cell culture

Tumoral cervical HeLa cell line was purchased from Cell Biolabs (San Diego, CA, USA), and T731 mice astrocytes were kindly donated by Prof. J. A. Costoya (University of Santiago de Compostela, Spain) and modified for overexpression of GFP (hereafter denoted as T731-GFP). Both cell lines were maintained at standard conditions (5 % CO_2 at 37°C) in

Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM), supplemented with 10 % (v/v) fetal bovine serum (FBS) and 1 % (v/v) penicillin/streptomycin, 1 % (v/v) sodium pyruvate, and 1 % (v/v) nonessential amino acids (NEAAs).

2.4. Cell viability

The biocompatibility of NCs was analyzed in HeLa and T731-GFP cell lines using the Cell Counting Kit-8 (CCK8) assay. In 96-well plates, HeLa and T731-GFP cells were seeded 5000 cells/well in 100 μL and incubated for 24 h. Afterwards, 100 μL of all NCs at different concentrations from 25 to 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ in the cell culture medium was added into the wells and incubated during 24, 48 and 72 h. The cells in the medium culture were used as the negative control. After incubation, the culture medium was removed, and the cells were washed with 10 mM PBS, pH 7.4, three times. Then, 90 μL of DMEM and 10 μL of CCK-8 cell proliferation reagent were added and incubated for 2 h. Next, the optical density of formazan was measured at 450 nm using a microplate absorbance reader (Bio-Rad model 689, Hercules, CA, USA). Cell metabolic activity was represented as the percentage of cell viability. It was calculated by normalizing the formazan optical density reading from cells exposed to NCS with that from the negative control (100 %) as follows:

$$Cell_{viability}(\%) = \frac{Abs_{sample}}{Abs_{control}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where Abs_{sample} is the absorbance at 450 nm for cells incubated with the solutions, and $Abs_{control}$ is the absorbance for negative control (only cells). Experiments were repeated five times.

2.5. Intracellular distribution assay

Cellular uptake of T731-GFP cells was performed by optical microscopy. The cells were seeded at a density of 1×10^5 per well in 2 mL in poly-L-lysine-coated glass coverslips ($12 \times 12 \text{ mm}^2$) placed inside 6-well plates and grown for 24 h at standard culture conditions (5 % CO_2 and 37°C). Afterwards, the culture medium was removed and replaced with 2 mL of SBA15-IO-1, SBA15-IO-1 T, SBA15-IO-2, and SBA15-IO-2 T at a 25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ concentration and incubated for 24 h. Then, the samples were washed three times with PBS at pH 7.4, and fixed with paraformaldehyde 4 % (w/v) for 10 min. Then, they were again washed with PBS and imaged. Microphotographs were randomly taken from samples.

2.6. Statistical analysis

All results were expressed as mean values with standard deviations. Statistical data evaluations were performed with Prism 9 software (GraphPad, Software, LLC). Two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Dunnett's multiple comparison tests was used to evaluate cell viability data. Values of $p < 0.05$ were considered statistically significant.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Structural and morphological characterization of SBA-15 matrices

The morphology of the SBA15-1 and SBA15-2 NCs was examined using TEM (Fig. 2.a and Fig. 2.b) and SEM (Fig. 2.e and Fig. 2.f) micrographs, clearly revealing the underlying hexagonal structure. Some morphological differences between the samples were evident, attributed to variations in the chemical parameters of the synthesis. The SBA15-1 sample displayed long filaments, while the SBA15-2 sample presented rod-shaped particles with a slight curvature, attributed to the presence of phosphoric acid [60]. Interestingly, the impact of heat treatment on the NCs revealed no significant changes in morphology and structure, as

Fig. 2. TEM micrographs of (a) SBA15-1, (b) SBA15-2, (c) SBA15-1 T and (d) SBA15-2 T NCs and SEM micrographs of (e) SBA15-1, (f) SBA15-2, (g) SBA15-1 T and (h) SBA15-2 T matrices.

Fig. 3. Nitrogen adsorption–desorption isotherms of (a) SBA15-1, (b) SBA15-2, (c) SBA15-1 T and (d) SBA15-2 T. Pore size distribution of (e) SBA15-1, (f) SBA15-2, (g) SBA15-1 T and (h) SBA15-2 T. Low angle X-ray diffraction patterns of (i) SBA15-1, (j) SBA15-2, (k) SBA15-1 T and (l) SBA15-2 T.

observed by TEM (Fig. 2.c and Fig. 2.d) and SEM (Fig. 2.g and Fig. 2.h) micrographs for the SBA15-1 T and SBA15-2 T NCs, respectively.

From the N_2 adsorption, type IV isotherms were obtained for all materials, as observed in Fig. 3 (a-d), which are characteristic of SBA-15 mesoporous materials. More specifically, a H_1 type hysteresis loop was observed with parallel adsorption and desorption branches, typical of cylindrical mesopores [61,62]. Relevant parameters such as surface area (S_{BET}) and pore volume (V_p), compiled in Table 2, were derived from the isotherms. Superior textural properties, with a larger S_{BET} and V_p , were obtained in the SBA15-2 NCs ($S_{BET} = 727.07 \text{ m}^2\text{g}^{-1}$; $V_p = 1.219 \text{ cm}^3\text{g}^{-1}$) compared to the SBA15-1 NCs ($S_{BET} = 639.29 \text{ m}^2\text{g}^{-1}$; $V_p = 0.954 \text{ cm}^3\text{g}^{-1}$), making this material a better choice for high-capacity loading purposes. However, once subjected to heat treatment, S_{BET} and V_p were clearly reduced. This aligns with previous works, where the densification experienced by silica at high temperatures is responsible for this

Table 2

Textural and structural values of SBA15-1, SBA15-2, SBA15-1 T and SBA15-2 T. Surface area (S_{BET}), pore volume (V_p), pore size by NLDFT method (PS_{DFT}), unit cell parameter (a_0), thickness of the wall of the mesopores ($t_{wall} = a_0 - PS_{DFT}$) and ζ -Potential.

Samples	S_{BET} (m^2/g)	V_p (cm^3/g)	PS_{DFT} (nm)	a_0 (nm)	t_{wall} (nm)	ζ -Potential (mV)
SBA15-1	639.29	0.954	8.15	12.43	4.29	-34.2
SBA15-2	727.07	1.219	8.15	12.43	4.29	-38.5
SBA15-1 T	472.32	0.496	3.88–6.27	9.29	2.99–5.41	-51.1
SBA15-2 T	214.30	0.312	2.56–5.10	8.83	3.73–6.27	-45.7

effect [63]. The pore size (PS_{DFT}) distribution of the materials was obtained by the Non-Local Density Functional Theory (NLDFT) method (see Table 2 and Fig. 3 (e-h)). A reduction in pore size was observed, from 8.15 nm of the initial untreated matrices (SBA15-1 and SBA15-2) to the two different pore sizes, 6.27 and 3.88 nm (SBA15-1 T) and 5.10 and 2.56 nm (SBA15-2 T) of the heat-treated matrices, respectively. The low-angle XRD patterns of SBA-15 matrices, shown in Fig. 3 (j-l), display a highly ordered 2D hexagonal structure, described by the $P6mm$ space group [54]. The three main peaks in the range of $0.75\text{--}2.00^\circ$ correspond to reflections from (100), (110) and (200) planes, associated with the long-range order of the mesoporous matrices. For the heat-treated matrices, a shift of the main peak towards higher values is observed, indicating a decrease of the lattice parameter from 12.43 nm to 9.29 nm for the SBA15-1 and SBA15-1 T, and from 12.43 nm to 8.83 for the SBA15-2 and SBA15-2 T, respectively, in agreement with previous works [63,64].

The functional groups present on the surface of the matrices were analyzed using FTIR spectroscopy to examine the vibrational bands (Figure S1), providing insights into the chemical topology. The formation of the siloxane matrix is evidenced by the presence of a stretching broad band at $1050\text{--}1025\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a bending band at $840\text{--}780\text{ cm}^{-1}$. On the other hand, the stretching band of free silanol is observed around $970\text{--}940\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the untreated matrices. However, a decrease in the silanol groups, identified by the absence of such band, is observed due to the heat treatment at 850°C . Other observable bands between 1630 cm^{-1} and 1325 cm^{-1} correspond to the adsorption of water molecules on the surface of the material. The peaks between 2900 and 3000 cm^{-1} and at 1480 cm^{-1} are ascribed to the stretching and bending modes of C-H bonds with sp^3 hybridization, respectively, and are attributed to the aliphatic chains of the remaining surfactant. The surfactant removal was carried out using the solvent extraction method, which made its complete elimination difficult due to the high porosity of the SBA-15 material. The broad band between 3700 and 3100 cm^{-1} corresponds to the O-H stretching mode of silanol groups. Post-heat treatment, a significant portion of the surfactant was removed from the pores, leading to the disappearance of some bands in Figure S1.

Colloidal stability was evaluated through ζ -Potential analysis, with the obtained values presented in Table 2. The analysis revealed an increase in the negative surface charge from -34.2 mV and -38.5 mV for the untreated matrices (SBA15-1 and SBA15-2, respectively) to -51.1 mV and -45.7 mV for the heat-treated matrices (SBA15-1 T and SBA15-2 T, respectively). The negative surface charge is associated with the presence of silanol groups from silica [65], and values exceeding $\pm 30\text{ mV}$ suggest stable dispersions due to interparticle electrostatic

repulsion, avoiding the presence of agglomerates [66]. Consequently, the application of heat treatment does not appear to compromise the stability of the matrices.

3.2. Structural and morphological characterization of magnetic NCs

The morphology of the NCs after the addition of MNPs was examined through SEM micrographs, specifically for SBA15-IO-1 (Fig. 4.a), SBA15-IO-1 T (Fig. 4.b), SBA15-IO-2 (Fig. 4.c), and SBA15-2 T (Fig. 4.d). The images evidence the preservation of the unmodified hexagonal SBA-15 morphologies with the visible presence of MNPs anchored in the outer layer of the SBA-15 matrix. TEM micrographs of magnetic NCs (Fig. 4) suggest the presence of MNPs inside the channels for the first set of NCs (SBA15-1 and SBA15-1 T), consistent with similar magnetic NCs synthesized through alternative routes [38,62]. This may be due to the synthesis characteristics of the first set of magnetic NCs, producing smaller-sized MNPs. Since the synthesis of MNPs was performed in situ with SBA-15 matrices, the Fe precursor compounds could penetrate inside the porous structure of SBA15, allowing the presence of MNPs within the channels. In contrast, the second set of magnetic NCs (SBA15-IO-2 and SBA15-IO-2), characterized by the formation of larger multi-core MNPs, displayed a higher presence of MNPs on the outside surface of the SBA-15 matrices. Nevertheless, the presence of MNPs inside the channels cannot be ruled out. Specifically, Fig. 4.g to 4.h indicate the formation of multicore nanostructures on the surface of SBA15-IO-2 and SBA15-IO-2 T NCs, while in SBA15-IO-1 and SBA15-IO-1 T NCs, a clustering of single-core MNPs appears diffusely organized on the silica surface. Furthermore, no structural alteration of the SBA-15 NCs was observed compared to their state before MNPs integration, even after heat treatment at 850°C .

XRD patterns of the magnetic NCs, observed in Figure S2, allow to elucidate the position and relative intensities of the main reflection peaks corresponding to magnetite or maghemite phase (ICSD 98-015-8742)[67], for the untreated NCs, and a combination of a magnetite phase (ICSD 98-008-2134 for SBA15-IO-1 and ICSD 98-015-8745 for SBA15-IO-2)[68,69] and hematite phase (ICSD 98-015-9975 for SBA15-IO-1 T and ICSD 98-016-4008 for SBA15-IO-2 T)[70], for the heat-treated NCs, resulting in NCs with new multiphase.

To assess the internal order of the mesoporous silica NCs, low angle X-ray diffraction was conducted (Figure S3), revealing a diffraction pattern with the three main reflections (100), (110) and (200), characteristic of the SBA-15 channel arrangement. In the patterns of SBA15-IO-1 and SBA15-IO-1 T NCs, a substantial reduction in intensity in the main peak (100) was observed, accompanied by the disappearance of

Fig. 4. SEM micrographs of the SBA-15 magnetic NCs: (a) SBA15-IO-1, (b) SBA15-IO-1 T, (c) SBA15-IO-2 and (d) SBA15-IO-2 T. TEM micrographs of the SBA-15 magnetic NCs: (e) SBA15-IO-1, (f) SBA15-IO-1 T, (g) SBA15-IO-2 and (h) SBA15-IO-2 T.

(110) and (200) reflections. This effect suggests a degradation in the long-range order of the matrix structure, possibly caused by the presence of MNPs distorting the SBA-15 channels [71] and adding randomness to the structure.

The effect of MNPs anchoring on the stability of mesoporous silica NCs was analyzed through ζ -Potential measurements. The SBA15-IO-1 sample revealed a positive surface charge value, 15.6 mV, attributed to the presence of a PEI coating on the MNPs [72]. After heat treatment, the surface charge of the SBA15-IO-1 T NCs became negative, measuring -41.3 mV. This change is attributed to the removal of the PEI coating due to high temperature. On the other hand, the second set of NCs revealed negative surface charges both before (-52.9 mV, SBA15-IO-2) and after treatment (-50.0 mV, SBA15-IO-2 T). Regarding the precursor NCs, SBA15-2 and SBA15-2 T, the anchoring of the MNPs on the surface of the NCs did not negatively affect their stability, with values above -30 mV (except for the SBA15-IO-1 NCs), suggesting stable dispersions.

3.3. Magnetic characterization

ZFC-FC curves in Fig. 5 revealed the superparamagnetic behavior below room temperature for the first set of magnetic NCs (Fig. 5.a), indicated by the presence of a maximum on the ZFC curve. Moreover, the second set of magnetic NCs exhibited ferrimagnetic behavior at room temperature (Fig. 5.b). It is noteworthy that the blocking temperature (T_B) increased from 33.24 K (SBA15-IO-1) to 82.83 K (SBA15-IO-1 T) after the thermal treatment. This shift suggests an increase in the effective anisotropy constant (K_{eff}) of the magnetic NCs, resulting from improved crystalline quality of the particles and enhanced dipole interactions among them, as a result of the heat treatment [73].

The magnetic hysteresis loops in Fig. 5 reveal lower magnetization and a stronger contribution from paramagnetic effects in the first set of NCs (SBA15-IO-1 and SBA15-IO-1 T), suggesting a smaller size and more magnetic disorder in the MNPs of these NCs compared to the MNPs of the second set of NCs (SBA15-IO-2 and SBA15-IO-2 T). This difference may be related to a lower degree of crystallization of the MNPs in the SBA15-IO-1 and SBA25-IO-1 T NCs. Relevant magnetic parameters such as saturation magnetization (M_S), coercivity (H_C), and remanence (M_R)

Table 3

Magnetic parameters of the NCs include the blocking temperature (T_B), which is obtained as the maximum of the ZFC curve, as well as the magnetic saturation (M_S), coercivity (H_C), and remanence (M_R) measured at 5 and 300 K from the hysteresis loops of Fig. 5.

Sample	T_B (K)	T (K)	M_S ($\text{Am}^2\text{kg}^{-1}$)	M_R ($\text{Am}^2\text{kg}^{-1}$)	H_C (kAm^{-1})
SBA15-IO-1	33.24	5	39.23	5.35	24.01
		300	12.85	0.22	1.35
SBA15-IO-1 T	82.83	5	40.15	9.09	58.95
		300	22.96	0.07	0.31
SBA15-IO-2	>350	5	69.55	19.20	17.07
		300	39.53	2.45	1.27
SBA15-IO-2 T	>350	5	27.51	8.58	23.05
		300	20.50	1.94	2.23

of all NCs were obtained and compiled in Table 3. It should be noted that, at $T = 300$ K, M_R and H_C were found to be close to zero for all NCs, suggesting superparamagnetic behavior. Of special importance is the thermal effect on the M_S variation. For SBA15-IO-1 NCs, an increase in M_S of almost twofold was observed at 300 K, which was not observed at 5 K. This magnetization enhancement agrees with the improvement in crystallinity due to the heat treatment observed in the X-ray patterns. On the contrary, for SBA15-IO-2, M_S was halved both at 300 K and 5 K after heat treatment (SBA15-IO-2 T). In summary, the obtained magnetization values in all NCs were significantly lower than that of bulk magnetite ($M_{S,\text{bulk}} = 92 \text{ Am}^2\text{kg}^{-1}$) [74], attributed to the reduced size of MNPs in the NCs. Moreover, the magnetization values were significantly higher than the bulk hematite M_S ($M_{S,\text{bulk}} = 0.3 \text{ Am}^2\text{kg}^{-1}$) [75], indicating the presence of other iron oxide phases in the heat-treated magnetic NCs.

To assess the influence of the internal structure and magnetic disorder effects, hysteresis loops were conducted at low temperatures under FC conditions, wherein a magnetic field is applied as the sample is cooled (refer to Figure S4). If spin disorder effects or the presence of different iron oxides phases are present, an exchange bias effect may emerge, leading to a shift of the hysteresis loops towards negative fields and positive magnetizations. This phenomenon has been attributed to

Fig. 5. Zero-field-cooled (ZFC) and field-cooled (FC) of (a) SBA15-IO-1 and SBA15-IO-1 T (d) SBA15-IO-2 and SBA15-IO-2 T at 7.95 kAm^{-1} . Hysteresis loops of SBA15-IO-1 and SBA15-IO-1 T NCs at (b) 5 K and (c) 300 K, and SBA15-IO-2 and SBA15-IO-2 T at (e) 5 K and (f) 300 K. The untreated magnetic NCs are represented by black patterns, while the heat-treated magnetic NCs are represented by orange patterns. Insets show the scale amplification of the hysteresis loops. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

the coupling between magnetic phases (typically ferromagnetic/anti-ferromagnetic) or the coupling between the internal spins [76,77]. The absence of this effect in the untreated NCs suggests the presence of a single dominant phase in the crystal structure, as observed in the X-ray diffractograms. However, once the NCs undergo heat treatment, exchange bias fields (H_{EB}), of up to 29.44 kAm^{-1} at 5 K appear for the SBA15-IO-1 T NCs, and a significantly lower value of 7.95 kAm^{-1} for the SBA15-IO-2 T NCs. This phenomenon, as observed by X-ray, suggests the presence of other Fe oxide phases in the heat-treated NCs that couple with each other. On the other hand, the higher H_{EB} in the SBA15-IO-1 T NCs may be due to the higher presence of disordered surface spins, consistent with the higher paramagnetic contribution observed in the hysteresis loops.

The interaction effects of the MNPs anchored in the SBA-15 matrix were investigated in the SBA15-IO-1 and SBA15-IO-1 T NCs due to their superparamagnetic properties, using AC magnetometry. Utilizing the Vogel Fulcher law, the parameter T_0 was determined, representing the temperature at which the relaxation time diverges (see Supporting Information and Figure S5 and S6). Obtained values of T_0 were $T_0 = 33.58 \text{ K}$ and $T_0 = 106.96 \text{ K}$, indicating an increase in T_0 following heat treatment, associated with heightened interactions [78]. This increase in interactions can be attributed to several reasons. Firstly, the removal of the PEI coating from MNPs of SBA15-IO-1 T at $850 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; despite its negligible thickness, this polymeric coating hinders exchange interactions between MNPs. Secondly, the transformation of iron oxide state from magnetite to a magnetite/hematite mixture may intensify aggregation effects due to the presence of hematite. [79].

3.4. Magnetic resonance imaging

An MRI signal study was performed introducing the NCs into agar-based phantom at different Fe concentrations. Fig. 6 shows the T_2 -weighted images obtained from low concentrations (left, control) to high concentrations (right, 0.25 mM Fe) of the first (Fig. 6.a) and second (Fig. 6.b) set of magnetic NCs before (top) and after (bottom) heat treatment. A clear increase in signal intensity respect to the water signal is obtained, showing the validity of NCs as negative contrast agents in MRI. T_2 -maps were generated through image processing, and r_2 was calculated as the slope of the curve resulting from fitting T_2^{-1} values against the Fe concentration of the magnetic material, as illustrated in

Fig. 6. T_2 -weighted images of agarose phantoms with increasing concentrations from 0.00 mM (control) to 0.25 mM of (a) SBA15-IO-1 and SBA15-IO-1 T and (b) SBA15-IO-2 and SBA15-IO-2 T NCs. Transverse relaxivity of (c) SBA15-IO-1 (grey dots) and SBA15-IO-1 T (red dots) and (d) SBA15-IO-2 (grey dots) and SBA15-IO-2 T (red dots) NCs. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 6.c/d. Interestingly, r_2 increased more than doubled in the first set of NCs due to the heat treatment, from $r_2 = 24.2 \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ mM}^{-1}$ (SBA15-IO-1) to $r_2 = 56.7 \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ mM}^{-1}$ (SBA15-IO-1 T). This significant increase is not observed in the second set of NCs, obtaining very similar values, from $r_2 = 29.9 \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ mM}^{-1}$ (SBA15-IO-2) to $r_2 = 25.9 \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ mM}^{-1}$ (SBA15-IO-2 T). While these nanoparticle contrast agents exhibit lower effectiveness compared to commonly used T_2 liver contrast agents, Resovist® ($r_2 = 61 \text{ mM}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$) or Feridex ($r_2 = 56.7 \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ mM}^{-1}$) at 1.5 T in water [80], it is crucial to note that global production and sales of both agents were halted in 2012 due to limited usage, with Resovist® now exclusively available as a liver agent in Japan [81]. Since the M_S directly affects the relaxivity values [82], the significant increase in the maximum magnetization of the SBA15-IO-1 NCs ($12.85 \text{ Am}^2 \text{ kg}^{-1}$) when heat treated, SBA15-IO-1 T NCs ($22.96 \text{ Am}^2 \text{ kg}^{-1}$), is reflected in the increase of the r_2 values in these NCs. Additionally, increased dipolar interaction effects from heat treatment may contribute to the enhanced r_2 . Although SBA15-IO-2 exhibited reduced magnetization post-heat treatment, this did not translate into a significant reduction in relaxivity.

3.5. Performance in magnetic hyperthermia processes

The performance of NCs for MH processes was investigated through two complementary approaches. Firstly, an analysis of the hysteresis curve derived from dynamic magnetization measurements was conducted. Secondly, an inductive heating device was employed to assess the performance. In the initial experiment, a volume of $V = 40 \text{ } \mu\text{L}$ of the NCs dispersed in water ($C = 4 \text{ g}_{\text{Fe}}/\text{L}$) was subjected to an AC magnetic field ($H = 20 \text{ kAm}^{-1}$; $f = 350 \text{ kHz}$). The resulting magnetization loop was quantified to calculate the specific absorption rate (SAR), expressed as $\text{SAR}_{\text{NTSOL}} = A \cdot f$, where A represents the magnetic area, and f denoted the AC magnetic field frequency. The hysteresis loops of all samples, observed in Fig. 7.a, (SBA15-IO-1 - black line, SBA15-IO-2 - gray line, SBA15-IO-1 T - orange line and SBA15-IO-2 T - blue line), revealed a notably smaller cycle for the SBA15-IO-1 and SBA15-IO-1 T NCs compared to the SBA15-IO-2 and SBA15-IO-2 T NCs. The corresponding magnitudes of the hysteresis area and SAR for each sample are compiled in Table 5, demonstrating a direct correlation among them.

Fig. 7.b shows the relationship between the $\text{SAR}_{\text{NTSOL}}$ values obtained through AC magnetometry and the H_C and M_S of the NCs in powder state acquired through DC measurements (solid dots) and

Fig. 7. (a) AC hysteresis loops under H_{AC} (20 kA/m and 350 kHz) at room temperature for the NCs: SBA15-IO-1 (black), SBA15-IO-1 T (orange), SBA15-IO-2 (gray) and SBA15-IO-2 T (blue). The iron content was 4 g_{Fe}/L for all measurements. (b) SAR_{NTSOL} value changes with H_C and M_S at 300 K in magnetic NCs: SBA15-IO-1 (black squares), SBA15-IO-1 T (orange circle), SBA15-IO-2 (gray triangle) and SBA15-IO-2 T (blue triangle) employing DC (SQUID, solid dots) and AC (AC Hyster Series, hollow dots). (c) Heating curves of SBA15-IO-1 (black), SBA15-IO-1 T (orange), SBA15-IO-2 (gray) and SBA15-IO-2 T (blue) NCs in a powdery state. (d) Temperature increase reached for 10 min and SAR obtained from these heating curves of the powered NCs (hollow dots and patterned columns) and the water-dispersed NCs (solid dots and columns). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

dispersed in water obtained through AC measurements (hollow dots). Generally, higher magnetization values were observed for DC measurements, and no discernible dependence on SAR values could be established. A clear correlation was observed between AC magnetization and SAR_{AC}, indicating higher SAR values for greater magnetization. On the other hand, the H_C obtained by DC ($H_{C-SQUID}$) generally presented lower values than those obtained by AC (H_{C-AC}), approaching zero in all samples. This increase in H_C from DC ($f = 0$ kHz) to AC ($f = 350$ kHz) measurements aligns with the transition from a superparamagnetic state to a blocked state above a certain blocking frequency observed in MNP systems [83]. Specifically, a direct relationship was observed between H_{C-AC} , notably higher for the SBA15-IO-2 and SBA15-IO-2 T NCs, and SAR.

In the second case, each specimen was positioned at the centre of a water-cooled hollow coil, where the RF magnetic field reached its maximum strength. The temperature variation over time was monitored using an optic-fiber thermometer, encompassing 10 min of magnetic field activation followed by 3 min of magnetic field deactivation to observe the cooling profile of the NCs. In the context of inductive heating devices, the heating efficiency of NCs could be quantified experimentally through the SAR_{MH}:

$$SAR_{MH} = \frac{P}{m_{NP}} = \frac{Q/\Delta t}{m_{NP}} = \frac{m_{NP}C_{NP} + m_{si-mesop}C_{si-mesop} + m_{water}C_{water}}{m_{NP}} \left(\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t} \right)_0 \quad (2)$$

where m_{NP} and $m_{si-mesop}$, m_{water} mass of iron oxide based MNPs, mesoporous silica matrix and water, were calculated after determining the

iron oxide weight percentage from FAAS. $C_{NP} = 0.746$ (Jg⁻¹K⁻¹), $C_{si-mesop} = 0.95$ (Jg⁻¹K⁻¹) and $C_{water} = 4.18$ (Jg⁻¹K⁻¹) are the specific heat of magnetite, mesoporous silica and water, respectively. The specific heat of mesoporous silica was determined following the methodology applicable to porous materials [84]. Nevertheless, in measurements based on powder samples, the Brown relaxation contribution was suppressed, leaving only the Néel contribution and hysteresis losses as the sole factors responsible for the heat generation of the NCs. This is expressed through the rewritten Eq. (2):

$$SAR_{MH} = \frac{P}{m_{NP}} = \frac{Q/\Delta t}{m_{NP}} = \frac{m_{NP}C_{NP} + m_{si-mesop}C_{si-mesop}}{m_{NP}} \left(\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t} \right)_0 \quad (3)$$

NCs were measured in both powdered state and water-based dispersions at $C = 4$ g_{Fe}L⁻¹. The heating curves for the NCs in powder state, as depicted in Fig. 7.c, exhibit notable temperature increases ($\Delta T < 30$ °C), except for SBA15-IO-1 NCs, showing their potential as nanoheaters. The temperature increments, depicted in Fig. 7.d and summarized in Table 4, reveal two distinct behaviors: In the first set of NCs, a higher amount of powdered magnetic material (6 mg) was required to achieve elevated temperatures, whereas in the second set, this amount was significantly reduced. Interestingly, the thermal effects resulted in an enhancement for the first set of NCs, with an increase in the SAR_{MH} from 0.52 to 2.42 Wg⁻¹, and a reduction for the second set of NCS, from 10.11 to 7.07 Wg⁻¹. This distinction positions the second set favorably for mild heat treatments, where the aim is to avoid the adverse effects of high temperatures such as tissue damages or necrosis within the brain [85]. The response in liquid media revealed higher SAR_{MH} values, as evident in

Table 4

Mass values used in the MH characterizations, SAR and temperature increase obtained under the application of a magnetic field of 20 mT and a frequency of 985 kHz for 10 min of the powered and water-disperse NCs.

Sample	Powdered Measurements				Water-Dispersed Measurements			
	Total mass (mg)	Magnetic mass (mg)	SAR (W/g)	ΔT (°C)	Volume (μL)	C ($\text{g}_{\text{Fe}}/\text{L}$)	SAR (W/g)	ΔT (°C)
SBA15-IO-1	23.3	6.0	0.52	12.08	200	4.0	4.11	3.59
SBA15-IO-1 T	23.3	6.0	2.42	32.67	200	4.0	6.17	4.78
SBA15-IO-2	2.0	0.2	10.11	37.07	200	4.0	93.77	18.66
SBA15-IO-2 T	7.5	0.8	7.07	43.65	200	4.0	19.56	9.04

Table 5

Coercivity (H_C), remanence (M_R) and maximum magnetization (M_{max}) obtained by DC(SQUID) and AC magnetometry and SAR and ILP values obtained by MH processes (SAR_{MH} and ILP_{MH}) and by AC magnetometry ($\text{SAR}_{\text{NTSOL}}$ and $\text{ILP}_{\text{NTSOL}}$).

Sample	$H_{C\text{-SQUID}}$ (kAm^{-1})	$M_{R\text{-SQUID}}$ ($\text{Am}^2\text{kg}^{-1}$)	$M_{\text{Max-SQUID}}$ ($\text{Am}^2\text{kg}^{-1}$)	$H_{C\text{-AC}}$ (kAm^{-1})	$M_{R\text{-AC}}$ ($\text{Am}^2\text{kg}^{-1}$)	$M_{\text{Max-AC}}$ ($\text{Am}^2\text{kg}^{-1}$)	SAR_{MH} (Wg^{-1})	$\text{SAR}_{\text{NTSOL}}$ (Wg^{-1})	ILP_{MH} ($\text{nHm}^2\text{kg}^{-1}$)	$\text{ILP}_{\text{NTSOL}}$ ($\text{nHm}^2\text{kg}^{-1}$)
SBA15-IO-1	1.3	0.2	12.9	0.7	0.1	4.0	4.11	3.8	0.01	0.03
SBA15-IO-1 T	0.3	0.1	22.9	0.6	0.1	4.5	6.17	3.4	0.02	0.02
SBA15-IO-2	1.2	2.4	39.5	6.6	4.1	11.6	93.77	89.4	0.39	0.64
SBA15-IO-2 T	2.2	1.9	20.5	5.3	2.6	9.7	19.56	60.3	0.08	0.43

Fig. 8. Cellular viability of SBA15-1, SBA-2, SBA-1 T, SBA-2 T, SBA15-IO-1, SBA15-IO-1 T, SBA15-IO-2, and SBA15-IO-2 T NCs in tumoral cervical HeLa cells for a) 24 h, b) 48 h, and c) 72 h and in T731 mice astrocytes cells for d) 24 h, e) 48 h, and f) 72 h as a function of concentration: (1) control, (2) $25 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, (3) $50 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, (4) $75 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, (5) $100 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, (6) $150 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and (7) $200 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

Fig. 7.d (solid columns) and Table 4, compared to the powdered NCs (patterned columns), attributed to the Brownian contribution, which is absent in the solid state. Notably, the thermal effect exhibited a similar trend in both NC sets, reaching the maximum SAR value for the SBA15-IO-2 NCs ($SAR_{MH} = 93.77 \text{ Wg}^{-1}$).

Under the assumption that the main SAR contribution for powdered NCs is Néel relaxation, and, for water dispersed NCs, it involves a combination of Brown and Néel relaxation, an enhancement in the Néel contribution of powdered NCs is evident after heat treatment. The estimated Néel contribution ($SAR_{MH-solid}/SAR_{MH-water-dispersed}$) for NCs pre-heat treatment is 12 % and 11 % for SBA15-IO-1 and SBA15-IO-2, respectively. This contribution improves to 39 % and 36 % for SBA15-IO-1 T and SBA15-IO-2 T, respectively, after heat treatment. This feature suggests a thermal process-induced enhancement of the Néel contribution in NCs. This enhancement is crucial in those systems where the Brownian contribution is suppressed due to the anchoring of MNPs to implantable devices or biological entities with high viscosity, with the Néel contribution being fundamental for heat generation.

Intrinsic loss power (ILP) values, as compiled in Table 5, were determined to compare the results obtained by the two distinct methods: MH measurements (ILP_{MH}) and AC magnetometry (ILP_{NTSOL}) due to the use of different experimental parameters (H and f). Higher values were obtained by AC magnetometry compared to MH measurements, especially notable in the SBA15-IO-2 T NCs, where a reduction from $0.43 \text{ nHm}^2\text{kg}^{-1}$ to $0.08 \text{ nHm}^2\text{kg}^{-1}$ was observed. This suggests that the accurate determination of the SAR from the heating curves might be influenced by experimental phenomena, such as the precipitation of the NCs over time or the limited diffusion of heat within the SiO_2 matrix.

3.6. Cell viability

The main parameter for assessing the safety of a nanocarrier is its biocompatibility. Firstly, this involves evaluating its interaction with cell cultures and subsequently, once fully optimized, conducting *in vivo* assays in animal models. For this reason, the biocompatibility of NCs was here preliminary evaluated *in vitro* to identify suitable administered concentrations and to analyze the potential inherent toxicity of the materials composing the nanocarrier. Then, the cell viability analysis of NCs was performed in two cell lines, HeLa and T731-GFP, to investigate specific cellular responses. The NCs were analyzed at different concentrations ($0 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and $200 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) at different incubation times, specifically 24, 48 and 72 h.

On the one hand, the survival rate of HeLa cells after NCs

administration is shown in Fig. 8. a-c. Cell viability remained above 80 % for SBA15-1, SBA15-2, SBA15-1 T, SBA15-IO-2, and SBA15-IO-2 T NCs after 24 h of incubation for all concentrations tested. Conversely, SBA15-2 T, SBA15-IO-1, and SBA15-IO-1 T NCs showed a cell viability of ca. 60 % at low concentrations (25 and $50 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) after 24 h, probably due to increased cellular uptake of these NCs. However, this behavior was not observed for longer incubation times, where viability significantly exceeded 80 % after 48 and 72 h, demonstrating that these NCs did not interfere with cell proliferation. In particular, except for SBA15-IO-1 NCs, all NCs showed viabilities above 80 %, confirming that HeLa cells could proliferate and survive even at high concentrations. Particularly, the relatively lower viability of SBA15-IO-1 may arise from the presence of the multicationically-charged PEI polymer on the NC surface, known to be toxic to cells beyond a certain concentration threshold and molecular weight [86]. For biomedical safety considerations, a cell survival rate of 80 % or higher is required [87]; therefore, all NC samples are deemed biocompatible at concentrations below $150 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$.

These NCs have been used in several biomedical applications, such as hyperthermia and magnetic resonance imaging [88]. Consequently, their assessment was extended to a mouse astrocyte cell line (T731-GFP) in order to take into account cell phenotype, since this can largely affect the biocompatibility of the nanocarriers [89]. Fig. 8.d-f illustrates NC viability in this cell line under conditions similar to those employed in experiments with the HeLa cell line. The experimental data showed that cell viability dropped below 80 % after 24 h at high concentrations, 150 and $200 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, particularly for MNP-doped NCs, even at lower concentrations. Notably, the reduction in cell survival became more pronounced at elevated particle concentrations, 150 and $200 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, especially for MNP-doped NCs. Interestingly, no significant reduction in viability was observed across all tested concentrations tested for both heat-treated and untreated non-doped NCs. In summary, the effect of doping with MNPs slightly increases the toxicity of the NCs, denoting that a concentration of $100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ is a critical threshold for safety [90]. Additionally, no negative effects were observed when NCs were subjected to heat treatment.

As previously mentioned, the cellular uptake of NCs during the initial 24 h is essential to correlate the potential toxic behavior exhibited by the MNP-doped NCs in cellular viability studies. To this end, the cellular uptake of NCs was analyzed in T731 mice astrocyte cell line at an initial NCs concentration of 25 mg mL^{-1} after 24 h of incubation using optical microscopy. Cell internalization of NCs was done for the MNP-doped NCs: SBA15-IO-1 (Fig. 9.c), SBA15-IO-1 T (Fig. 9.d), SBA15-IO-2 (Fig. 9.e) and SBA15-IO-2 T (Fig. 9.f) and bare astrocytes used as

Fig. 9. Optical images of T731 cells a,b) without uptake of NCs (control) and after uptake during a 24-hour incubation period at a concentration of $25 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of the c) SBA15-IO-1, d) SBA15-IO-1 T, e) SBA15-IO-2 and f) SBA15-IO-2 T magnetic NCs.

control (Fig. 9.a. and b) since undoped SBA15 matrices had an excellent cellular viability at all conditions. The images showed that the elongated morphology of the cells remained unaffected upon the addition of MNP-doped NCs. Nevertheless, the SBA15-IO-1 and SBA15-IO-1 T NCs exhibited a greater number of NCs internalized, probably due to the positive charge imparted by the PEI coating. This positive charge might favor some electrostatic interactions with the negatively charged cellular environment, thereby promoting cell uptake, and increasing contrast enhancement for biomedical imaging [91]. In addition, the uptake mechanism has been demonstrated to depend on the NCs coating; however, in this case, the absence of any receptor-mediated mechanisms suggests nonspecific endocytosis, as previously reported for these NCs [92,93].

In summary, the noticeable cellular uptake and biocompatibility of NCs in two cell lines can be confirmed under the different conditions analyzed. As observed, cellular internalization is higher in PEI-coated NCs, even at low concentrations, owing to their inherent surface positive charge. Consequently, cell survival for these NCs was initially slightly lower than for other samples after 24 h; however, this did not affect the proliferation capacity of cells at longer incubation times.

4. Conclusions

In this work, mesoporous silica NCs incorporating MNPs were prepared and tailored to enhance their magnetic behavior for application in both MRI and MH. The host material utilized for these NCs was SBA-15 mesoporous silica matrices, characterized by controlled pore structure and a large surface area. MNPs were introduced into the silica matrix through both in-situ synthesis and external attachment. Subsequent heat treatment was employed to optimize the magnetic properties of the NCs, with detailed magnetic assessments conducted in both direct current (DC) and alternating current (AC). This optimization led to improved magnetic responses to external magnetic fields, particularly evident in the increase of r_2 values in MRI, from $24.2 \text{ mM}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ to $56.7 \text{ mM}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ for the first set of magnetic NCs (SBA15-IO-1 and SBA15-IO-1 T), and from $29.9 \text{ mM}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ to $25.9 \text{ mM}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ for the second set of magnetic NCs (SBA15-IO-2 and SBA15-IO-2 T). Furthermore, the heat-treated NCs exhibited enhanced Néel relaxation effects during MH, with the percentage rising significantly from 12 % and 11 % (SBA15-IO-1 and SBA15-IO-2) to 39 % and 36 % (SBA15-IO-1 T and SBA15-IO-2 T). This straightforward method for controlling and optimizing magnetic properties proves to be an efficient and easily reproducible means of enhancing the performance of these NCs, potentially facilitating their clinical applications. Furthermore, biological assays conducted on two cell lines, HeLa and T731 astrocytes, demonstrated low toxicity even at concentrations up to $200 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, confirming the safety of these NCs as drug delivery platforms. In summary, this method significantly improved the performance of SBA-15-based NCs for theranostic applications, all while maintaining their structural integrity.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Pelayo García-Acevedo: Writing – original draft, Conceptualization, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Zulema Vargas-Osorio:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation. **Brenda Velasco:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation. **Manuel A. González-Gómez:** Investigation, Data curation. **Angela Arnosa-Prieto:** Investigation, Data curation. **Lisandra de Castro-Alves:** Investigation, Data curation. **Ramón Iglesias-Rey:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Pablo Taboada:** Resources, Supervision, Project administration, Writing – review & editing. **Yolanda Piñeiro:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **José Rivas:** Resources, Supervision, Project administration, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

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